

Reliability Analysis of Multi Element Integrated Testing in Space Systems

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Key Words: Hardware-Software-Human Reliability, System Reliability, Interface Reliability, Integrated Systems

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the analyses of a methodology to capture quantitative reliability from multi element integrated systems of processing environments of the International Space Station (ISS) Program at the Kennedy Space Center (KSC) in Florida. The analysis uses the combination of Baker's Generic Classification Scheme, Goodness of Fit and the Laplace techniques to classify the multi-element integrated systems within processes into single (human, hardware, software), dual (hardware-software, software-human, human-hardware), and multi elements (hardware-software-human) interactions. The technique provides practitioners with immediate statistical significance of reliability growth or deterioration in a process. The significance of research lies within the inclusion of first order element interactions of dual and multi elements to properly estimate standard reliability. Qualitative and quantitative decisions are made to understand mechanisms across simulated and operationally configured tests (at the system, subsystem, element, element interaction, and element attributes levels) as well as scrutinize certain problems within steps of various sequenced processes. The analyses mark the first time a logically statistical technique is utilized in an integrated approach to assess total system reliability of simultaneous failures in real field performance. The overall reliability assessment reflects process success rate over the development test time.

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of a multi element integrated testing to estimate total system reliability is relevant to the studies because too often reliability is overestimated because of the lack of knowledge at the interfaces. Too often multi-elements (hardware-software-human) are not calculated as a first order interaction of standard reliability.

The NASA Space Transportation System or Shuttle is a multi element system that launches space exploration experiments in orbit. During a pilot study of the past ten years, reliability issues were centered on multi-element failures, not single element reliability seen in literature. There were no operational analysis methods to thoroughly analyze the system reliability of such inseparable frameworks. The operation method analysis of this paper examines failures that occur during processing through hypothesis testing on Baker's classification scheme, Kilgomorv Smirnov's distribution fitting and Laplace's trend testing.

The logically statistical technique applied to the problem reporting system of a processing environment of the International Space Station Program is utilized to classify, identify, analyze and measure reliability. By understanding ISS processing environment, practitioners will be able to better understand ground processing phenomena and extend this knowledge to on orbit tasks for Station. Although the generic technique can be applied to any a system, the space system offers a higher, universal industry domain of a safety-critical and controlled environment. The methodology is this paper concentrates on the interface of these elements and their interactions during the lifecycle checkout of the Multi-Element Integrated Testing (MEIT, Phase1, TC2R) for the ISS Program.

As all NASA Centers strive to become "One NASA", the analyses of this paper provide process improvement opportunities to the practitioners in spite of recent news briefs concerning ISS Program funding and software problems.

2. METHODOLOGY

The processing environment of the ISS Program is composed of multi element integrated systems that identify single, dual and multi element failures. The operational methodology utilizes Test Configuration 2R, comprised of the Command and Data Handling (CDH), Command and Tracking (CT), Electrical Control System (ECS), Guidance and Navigation Control (GNC) and Thermal Control System (TCS) processing subsystems of Phase 1. The failures in testing procedures are recorded during the practitioner training of a simulated environment and compares it to the primary testing facility of an operationally configured environment.

The MEIT describes failures of inseparable frameworks from a binary system, operational or failing. For instance, system 1, system 2, and system 3 are composed as a multi-element integrated system (see Figure 1). System 1 has a hardware failure that is connected to a hardware-software-human failure in system 2. System 2 is connected to a software-human failure in system 3. Although the human does not come into the scenario until the introduction of system 2, all three systems compose a complex integrative system and are connected by the human intervention. Pasquini et al (Ref. 1) state that it is very hard to even study humans when the human is not isolated from the external hardware and/or software being utilized.

Figure 1: Multi-element integrated systems

The integrated systems approach extends the knowledge of Pasquini's (Ref. 1) experimental trend testing on dual elements and Bodsberg's (Ref. 2) classification theory of the physical and functional nature of failures to multi-element integrated testing systems. This paper displays the analysis of three-way failure existence as significant contributors to reliability estimation of multi-element integrated systems.

2.1 Data Generation

Field data is gathered during the operational Phase 1 of the MEIT system into a problem reporting system. A problem report identifies the conditions, inputs, and equipment configuration for which the problem arises, a description of the activities leading up to the issue, and sufficient information to permit issue duplication and analysis. The issue description must completely describe the issue such that the analyst has the whole problem prior to comprehending the scope of the issue. If the issue was identified during a usage or operational scenario, the product configuration should also include hardware configuration, test or operational procedure, screen or display upon which the issue was identified.

In process testing environments, training is a known contributor to the overall reliability of an integrated system that involves the hardware, software, and human elements. In an operational life cycle, the way training is received and implemented depends on the technology of the hardware, technology of the software system, and the experience of the human. Training may be provided as written (hardware), oral (human), or computer (software) instructions. The system experts of MEIT Phase 1 are all engineering and software technicians located in Houston and Florida. Once a failure occurs, the expert tracks the root cause of the failure and testing does not resume until contributing causes are identified and fixed "as good as new". The human knowledge responds to the problems as they arise and aids in the exactness of the problem being reported and resolved.

Training for the applied technique of this paper includes quality engineering experts from Florida where all operational testing is performed. The expert analyst reviewed and extracted how and where problems occurred to determine the interaction of elements based on the descriptive event. The expert would then assign an attribute to the element or element interaction. The total reviewing of resolutions lasted for 5 months.

Attributes are typically chosen when consumers shop for the most reliable and robust service and product available. An attribute is considered to be either a contributing characteristics that helps a system perform properly or aids the system in not functioning properly. To utilize a particular

attribute means a contribution to a system's failure associated with the state of the system. The attributes of Table 1 serve as quality and significant contributors in measuring the total reliability of the any system. Attribute interactions are comprised from crossing a single element's attributes with those of another single element that create many three-way interactions. The nine consistent dual and multi-elements patterns repeatedly shown in the processing test of the ISS are listed in Table 2.

Hardware	Software	Human
(1) Maintenance	(1) Structural	(1) Mental acuity
(2) Existence	(2) Logic	(2) Physical Ability
(3) Environment	(3) Coding	(3) Experience years
(4) Technology	(4) Input hypothesis	(4) Training
(5) Warranty		(5) Human involvement
(6) Compatibility		(6) Nature of task

Table 1. Baker's Element Attributes for Generic Integrated Models

Pattern	HW	SW	Man
OOO	0	0	0
131	1	3	1
614	6	1	4
32X	3	2	
4X6	4		6
61X	6	1	
63X	6	3	
6X4	6		4
X14		1	4
X21		2	1
X31		3	1

Table 2: ISS nine significant attributes

2.2 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is the probabilistic technique used in assigning elements, element interactions, and element attributes to root causes. This particular part of the methodology occurs in three phases, classification, distribution, and trending.

The classification phase categorizes failures as single, dual, or multi-element interactions. The focus of the hypothesis testing in classification is to determine whether three-way (hardware-software-human) failures occur. The techniques examine the null hypothesis of a failure being a three-way failure versus the failure not being a three-way failure. The failure is always classified because by trying to identify the failure as three-way enhances capturing the failure to be a dual or single element.

Distribution fitting in hypothesis testing examines the theoretical distribution to the empirical distribution by use

of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test. The null hypothesis states that the sample is a specific theoretical distribution and the alternatives state the sample is not a specific distribution. Simple distribution assumptions are not automatically justified because the data is not necessarily independent and identically distributed.

Once complete hypothesis testing is conducted, reliability estimation is measured from the success rate and time to failure of the problems reported during processing of MEIT Phase 1, TC2R. Phases are compared to report pliable environments between simulated and operational testing on earth and mission testing in space.

2.3 Applied Methodology

The methodology applied to the system in its operational phase focuses on the existence of significant multi-elements to the standard reliability equation (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_S &= 1 - F_S \text{ (probability of failure)} \\
 &= 1 - \{ \text{Element Failure} + \text{Interaction Failure} \} \\
 &= 1 - \{ [F_{HW} + F_{SW} + F_{MAN}] - [F_{SW-MAN} + F_{HW-MAN} \\
 &+ F_{HW-SW}] - F_{SW-HW-MAN} \}. \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Attribute patterns, attached to failures, easily explain specific circumstances that occurred in certain locations through processing. The contributing dual and multi-elements determined from the performance of both test are provided in Table 2. Other dual and multi-elements were found but not enough data points existed to state dominance. The empirical distributions of the attribute patterns pinpoint systemic problems across test, subsystems, and elements. Engineers are able to compare empirical distributions with theoretical distributions for Goodness-of-Fit and simply calculate trends of reliability growth or deterioration.

The time of sequence of a failure with its attribute pattern provide MTBF. These reliability measures were compared to the standard reliability equation measures. Since there were not enough similar failure data points in this particular testing configuration, a failure's MTBF was utilized in comparison to its sequence-step, survival rate measures rather than the standard reliability equation. The correlation between the survival rate of sequences and the MTBF was similar in some elements but not all.

Reliability can be provided by the standard reliability equation given enough data points in complete operational testing. However, the main focus is to identify significant three-way or multi-element failures. These failures were extracted then included and excluded in distributions of tests, subsystems, and elements to state their impact to total system reliability estimation.

3. ANALYSES

The multi-element integrated model was developed to evaluate the reliability of the simulated and operationally configured testing by system, element, and element attribute interaction. The most significant single, dual, multi, and attribute elements are analyzed for both tests. A complete reliability comparison is presented for discussion in Section 4.

3.1 Process Testing

Process testing of a unique checkout system was performed on the simulated and operationally configured test of the test configuration 2R of the multi-element integrated testing of the ISS. All failures encountered during process testing are used in the distribution for each test regardless of element or subsystem. The focus of the integrated model is to see how effective and significant hardware-software-human interactions would be on the estimation of total system reliability. The significance of each model was determined by trending analysis of the distribution on the elements interaction, element attribute interaction and system. The characteristics of a significant distribution lie within process success rate change over the development test time.

The K-S test was only used to determine process distribution fitting in simulated and operationally configured test. The table shows that the computed value of the K-S for the simulated test is 3.926 and 2.475 for the operationally configured test. Using the modified K-S to test the upper tail at the 95% confidence level, the null hypothesis is rejected that either case is representative of the normal distribution. Distribution fitting was considered for the overall process of a case test, not for individual elements. As an individual element, elements were studied from a reliability growth or deterioration standpoint with the Laplace test.

The test statistic values in the Laplace test for simulated and operationally configured test are -.9212 and -1.654, respectively. These values state that both cases have trend data. The values being less than zero state that within the entire test of each case there was reliability growth. It further shows that operationally configured test became more negative so there was more growth present from the simulated to operational test. This is exactly the significance the study of reliability growth distributions was to reveal.

3.1.1 Simulated testing

Simulated testing occurred for 16 days at 10 hours each day. The total number of sequences for the entire test is. The data set considers 78 failure points to be classified, statistically tested, and assigned reliability measures.

The reliability process distribution for the simulated test is shown in Figure 2. The hardware-software-human (Figure 3) interaction of the simulated test demonstrates enough significance to be included as a standard reliability estimator. This phenomenon has never been considered in the reliability estimation of previous research. Figure 4 shows the process distribution without the hardware-software-human failures.

Figure 2: Simulated Test: Reliability Distribution

In this particular test, the hardware-software-human interactions are fairly significant. However, the more significant element interaction is the dual interaction, software-human (Figure 5). Element-attributes are the specific attributes of interactions that let the designer know what type of problems were significant. Most of the software-human interactions have the pattern X30 (Figure 6), the 0 meaning the human may have pushed a command as his/her participation, but there lies great concern with the software and how the coding related to the commands.

Figure 3: Simulated test: HW-SW-Man interactions

Figure 4: Simulated test: Reliability Distribution without HW-SW-Man interactions

Figure 5: Simulated test: SW-Man, the most significant dual interaction

Figure 6: Simulated test, the most significant dual attribute

The configuration of both test included five subsystems that are analyzed as components to give the reliability of the system. The most prevalent system for this particular test is CD&H (Figure 7), stating that more problems were found in this system. The CD&H does contain the most hardware-software-human failure points of all mentioned systems. However, this system can still have the most growth. Referencing systems, Figure 8 shows the most significant element and element attribute interaction is between HW-SW (61X) and SW-Man (X30). On attribute 61X, all the problems are concentrated in one particular area, the very beginning of the operations manual.

Figure 7: Simulated test, the most significant system

Figure 8: Simulated test: S1 (61X), (X30)

3.1.2 Operationally configured testing

The operationally configured testing was performed in 12, three-hour shift days with 95 failure points. The total number of sequences for the entire test is 75 with 3407 individual steps.

The reliability growth distribution for the operationally configured test is shown in Figures 9 and 10 with and without hardware-software-human data points respectively. In this test, the hardware-software-human interaction proves to have a good contribution to reliability. However, the most significant element interaction of the test is software with the human interaction not too far behind (Figure 11). The contributing element attribution is within software coding (X3X). The significant attribute for the human interactions is in training (XX4).

Figure 9: Operationally configured test: Reliability Growth Distribution

Figure 11: Operationally configured test, most significant element interaction

When it comes to displaying the failures, the software attributes appeared with great significance in each attribute X2X, X3X, and X4X. This contends to the fact that extreme software problems exist across both tests. The problems are spread throughout the individual software attributes versus the concentrated effect we saw earlier. The predominant system of the operationally configured test is the CD&H system. Its growth is slightly higher (meaning more negative) than ECS and GNC (see Figure 12). C&T and TCS of Figure 13 show deterioration in reliability. Compared to the systems of simulated tests, operationally configured test have more failures to display.

Figure 12: Operationally configured test: Systems with reliability growth

Figure 13: Operationally configured: Systems with deterioration

4. DISCUSSION

Reliability comparisons are made to examine the success rate, MTBF, and GOF tests of all elements presented through this paper. The success rate and MTBF were more related in the simulated testing than configured testing. The guidelines to determine uncertainty of several failures in configured testing may have been offset by the time conversion technique.

Hypothesis testing proved the existence of hardware-software-human failures and affirmed a multi-element integrated model to quantify failures. The analysis also confirmed that traditional assumptions of MTBF (Ref. 4) are not permitted in unique environments without thorough investigation into the nature of data. The Laplace test examined trends that proved some operations were worked out of sequence with either reliability growth or deterioration of non-independent and identically distributed data across tests, subsystems, elements, and element-attributes. The information provides the results to necessarily monitor the action of the subsystems, elements and element attributes from simulated and operationally configured test.

All elements failures among the test cases showed that reliability increased 80% from the simulated to the operationally configured test. Hardware-software-human element distributions show great reliability increase from the simulated to the configured test. Three-way failures of the simulated test demonstrated enough significance to contribute to the standard reliability equation. However, the hardware and hardware-human contributions to either test were slim and the standard reliability equation could not be applied. Three-way failures of the configured test demonstrate more reliability growth than the simulated test.

When examining MTBF in both test cases, the average occurrence of failures happened around 46% of complete processing. The reliability of hardware-software-human failures from survival rates was around 55% with a 5%

confidence interval. The MTBF was 55% reliable for the simulated and 41% reliable for the configured test. This is over a 10% difference that may be attributed to the correlation between the survival steps and time.

The overall reliability of elements and their interactions demonstrated how reliability is determined for the standard reliability equation. Some elements were not applicable because each group needed at least 4 data point to provide conclusiveness. The Laplace, MTBF, or success rate utilizes $n-1$ (instead of n) data points when the last data value of the set determines the total time of failure for the element system. The best case of overall reliability assessment is not determined because of the non-applicability (N/A) of elements of simulated being applicable to operationally configured and vice versa. The K-S tests verified that the data is not independent and identically distributed. The reliability growth distribution of the entire case did prove to be favorable from simulated to operationally configured test with the Laplace. The Laplace test for individual element and element interaction contributors depicted that more deterioration existed across cases than growth itself.

The subsystems are easier to compare than the element attributes. Subsystems CDH, CT, ECS, and TCS are significant to both tests. CDH shows much more reliability growth from simulated test to operationally configured test. Although reliability growth is present from simulated to operationally configured test, ECS shows a decrease in reliability. Subsystem TCS shows hardly any significant growth of reliability for simulated test but operationally configured shows deterioration.

In conclusion, the total reliability of multi-elements systems has been acquired and assessed by hypothesis testing and quantitative measurement, respectively. Although the standard reliability equation is sufficient to calculate element and element interactions, it was not used because some of the element and element interactions did not have enough data points. This does not mean that the element did not show up in hypothesis testing. It only means that the research did not overestimate reliability as seen in previous studies.

Future research will include looking at the same tests configurations in Phase 2 and Phase 3 to detect reliability growth improvement for cases, elements, element-attributes, and subsystems; analyzing on-orbit data; and investigating element attributes as a network to better understand the system as a predictive measure.

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